

Feto-Maternal Outcome in Placenta Previa in Scarred Uterus and Unscarred Uterus**Sharadha Govindaraju¹, Annu Murali M², Bhanumathi Vasudeva³, Syeda Maisarah Imam⁴, Suresh S Kanakannavar⁵**^{1,2,3,4}Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Vani Vilas, BMCRI, Bangalore India⁵Professor of Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, Bangalore, India

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Syeda Maisarah Imam

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** In placenta previa, the placenta attaches lower in the uterus. This results in some portion of the placental tissue covering the lower uterine segment. It can result in bleeding during the pregnancy or during or after delivery.**Objective:** to determine the frequency of placenta previa and to determine the risk factors and feto-maternal outcomes in placenta previa in previously unscarred and scarred uterus groups.**Methods:** This is an observational study which involved 130 patients diagnosed with placenta previa after satisfying the inclusion criteria. The demographic data, maternal morbidity indicators, maternal mortality, fetal parameters morbidity parameters like prematurity, low birth weight and need for ICU admission as well as mortality parameters such as still births and neonatal mortality rates.**Results:** Mean age of the study population was 27.12±4.426 years. Incidence of placenta previa among scarred uterus was 1.32% and in unscarred uterus was 0.67%. High parity, high abortion rate, multigravida status, less gestational age at delivery were commonly seen in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. Causes of scarred uterus in this study was previous LSCS (54.61%), previous D&C (10.8%) and previous myomectomy (10%).

Complete placenta previa, anterior placental position and adherent placenta were significantly associated with scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. Antepartum hemorrhage and postpartum hemorrhage was higher in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. Rate of caesarean hysterectomy was higher in scarred uterus, along with statistical association to previous LSCS. Maternal ICU admission rate was higher in scarred group, also showed its statistical association with previous LSCS. Neonatal outcomes in terms of pre-term birth, still birth, NICU admission and neonatal death though higher in scarred group, did not differ statistically among both the groups.

Conclusions: This study highlighted the therapeutic implication of placenta previa and its management along with risk factors in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus.**Keywords:** Placenta Previa, Scarred Uterus, Adherent Placenta, Fetomaternal Outcome.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Placenta previa is an obstetric condition in which placenta is implanted partially or wholly in lower uterine segment. Placenta previa is classified by the degree of encroachment upon the internal cervical os. Placenta previa occurs approximately one of every 250 births. More than one third of all antepartum haemorrhage occurs due to placenta previa. In complete placenta previa, the cervical os is completely covered by the placenta. In partial placenta previa, the cervical os is partly covered by the placenta. In marginal placenta previa, the edge of the placenta is considered to be at the margin of the internal os. The term low-lying placenta is described as a placental edge that approaches to within 2 cm of the cervix on ultrasound examination.

The most accurate measurement is obtained by transvaginal ultrasound scanning. Placenta accreta is defined as an abnormal adherence of the placenta to the uterine wall owing to an absent or faulty decidua basalis. Separation of the placenta accreta from the uterine wall can result in fatal hemorrhage. Placenta percreta can lead to bowel injury, bladder injury, life-threatening hemorrhage, coagulopathy, amniotic fluid embolism, and peripartum hysterectomy. The incidence of this devastating problem is increasing secondary to the increased incidence of caesarean section. Placenta accreta, increta, and percreta occur much less frequently, from 1 in 1600 to 1 in 12,000 patients. Placenta accreta occurs most commonly, followed in de-

creasing frequency by placenta increta and placenta percreta. For our purposes, we refer to all three conditions under placenta accreta. Confirmation of placenta accreta requires histopathologic methods, and so it is possible that incidence is underreported when the condition is focal or not associated with performance of a hysterectomy.

Patients presenting with abnormal placental attachment have a complicated surgical course and a high mortality rate. Anaesthetists should be prepared to manage massive blood loss by using effective teamwork, leadership, and communication strategies. Technical skills are paramount to reaching the goal of a positive outcome for mother and baby. The obstetrician and the obstetric anaesthesiologist must know, on-the-spot, how to deal with this problem.

So, in this study, we want to help identify those women with high risk factors during the antenatal period for early diagnosis, timely intervention and prompt management to reduce maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective observational study was conducted among patients attending OPD/IPD in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Department Vani Vilas attached to Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, from February 2021 to August 2022 were included in the study.

Sampling technique: Computer generated simple random sampling numbers.

Sample Size Calculation: The sample size was calculated as 100.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients who give consent to participate in the study.
2. All pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa beyond 28 weeks of gestation at or after admission are included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients not willing to participate in the study.
2. Gestational age < 28 weeks.
3. Other causes of antepartum bleeding.
4. Multiple pregnancy.
5. Pregnant women with hypertension, gestational diabetes and other
6. Comorbid conditions.

Methodology:

After obtaining approval and clearance from the institutional ethics committee, the patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled for the study after obtaining informed consent.

Gestational age was calculated using LMP and

EDD as per the earliest first trimester scan. Diagnosis was confirmed by transabdominal and transvaginal ultrasound as and when required. MRI was done to rule out adherent placenta. The cases were divided into two groups:

- A. Unscarred uterus- including cases with placenta previa who have no previous history of cesarean section or any uterine surgery like curettage.
- B. Scarred uterus - including cases with placenta previa who have a history of 1 or more previous cesarean section or uterine surgery like myomectomy or uterine rupture repair.

Both the groups were compared for parameters such as maternal age, parity, previous obstetric history, mode of delivery, type and grading of placenta, maternal morbidity indicators such as postpartum hemorrhage, need for blood transfusions, need for ICU admission, need for caesarean sections and other extra surgical maneuvers to control excessive bleed, maternal mortality, fetal parameters such as fetal malpresentations, fetal morbidity parameters like prematurity, low birth weight and need for ICU admission as well as mortality parameters such as still births and neonatal mortality rates. All the required information was collected in pre-structured and pretested proforma to fulfill objectives of study.

Statistical Analysis: The data was entered into MS Office Excel and analysed using SPSS version 20.0 Sociodemographic data was presented using descriptive statistics namely mean, median, standard deviation, percentage wherever applicable. The CHI SQUARE TEST or T TEST was used to compare the data as appropriate. P value of <0.05 was considered significant. Data is presented in the form of tables, figures and graphs wherever necessary.

Results

Total of 21767 deliveries done in 2years. And a total of 190 cases of placenta previa, among whom, 88 patients had scarred uterus and 102 had unscarred uterus. Incidence of placenta previa in our tertiary care hospital was 0.876%. Incidence of placenta previa in the scarred uterus group was 1.32% and in unscarred uterus group, incidence was 0.67%. Mean age of participants with scarred uterus was 27.74 years and among unscarred uterus, it was 26.12 years.

Among patients with scarred uterus, 78.75% were booked pregnancies and 21.25% were unbooked. Among patients with unscarred uterus, 78% were booked pregnancies and 22% were unbooked. Prior antenatal records of patients were assessed.

A pregnant woman is said to be booked if she attended at least four antenatal clinic visits, received at least 1 dose of tetanus immunization and was

administered at least 100 IFA tablets during her pregnancy. Majority of the unscarred uterus (92%) were nulliparous and only 8% with scarred uterus were nulliparous women. Among the primiparous women, 73.4% had scarred uterus (scarring due to prior myomectomy, D & C) and 26.4% had unscarred uterus. Among the multi-parous women, 90.3% had scarred uterus and 29% had unscarred uterus. Parity status showed significant difference between the scarred and unscarred uterus.

80.5% of women with scarred uterus and 19.4% with unscarred uterus had abortions. Scarred uterus showed statistically significant associations with abortions.

Mean gestational age in unscarred uterus was 36.51 weeks and in scarred uterus was 35.53 weeks.

Scarred Uterus

Majority of the patients had one or two LSCS (54.61%) as mode of delivery. 10.8% underwent D and C previously. One patient had history of previous myomectomy. Among the unscarred uterus, 82% of patients underwent emergency LSCS and 18% underwent elective LSCS. Among the scarred uterus, 85% of patients underwent emergency LSCS and 15% underwent elective LSCS. Among cases of scarred uterus, low lying placenta was seen in 20% and complete placenta previa was seen in 80%. Among cases of unscarred uterus, low lying placenta was seen in 54% cases and complete placenta was seen in 56%. Cases Among cases of scarred uterus, 51.25% had anterior placenta and 48.75% had posterior placenta. Among cases of unscarred uterus, 73% had posterior placenta and 28% had anterior placenta. Anterior loca-

tion of placenta is statistically associated with scarred uterus. In scarred uterus, 82.5% had no invasion, 10% had placenta accreta, 3.7% had increta and 3.7% had percreta. Placenta accrete spectrum is statistically associated with scarred uterus.

Statistically significant association was observed between the previous LSCS and complete placenta previa. APH did not show statistically significant association with previous LSCS. 74.5% cases of scarred uterus and 25.4% cases of unscarred uterus had PPH. PPH showed statistically significant association with previous LSCS.

All patients who underwent caesarean hysterectomy had scarred uterus (21.25%). hysterectomy showed statistically significant association with previous LSCS. 50% cases of scarred uterus and 50% cases of unscarred uterus needed compression sutures. B-Lynch sutures was applied to 12 cases (5 scarred and 7 unscarred). Hayman sutures was applied to 5 cases (3 scarred and 1 unscarred). 68% cases of scarred uterus and 32% cases of unscarred uterus needed uterine artery ligation. 79.1% cases of scarred uterus and 20.8% cases of unscarred uterus underwent iliac artery ligation. Scarred uterus showed statistically significant association with iliac artery ligation. One patient with scarred uterus underwent bakri balloon procedure. 4 patients with scarred uterus had accidental intraoperative bladder injury.

Maternal Outcomes

90% of ICU admissions was observed among cases of scarred uterus and 10% among cases of unscarred uterus.

Table 1: association of previous number of LSCS with ICU admission

		ICU Admission		Total	P value
		yes	no		
Previous No of LSCS	NA	2	57	59	0.000
	1	9	44	53	
	2	9	9	18	
Total		20	110	130	

ICU admission showed significant association with previous LSCS. One death observed in unscarred uterus.

Table 2: association of maternal mortality with previous LSCS

		MM Code		Total	P Value
		Yes	No		
Previous No of LSCS	NA	1	58	59	
	1	0	53	53	0.454
	2	0	18	18	
Total		1	129	130	

Maternal mortality did not show association with previous LSCS. 40% cases of scarred uterus and 24% cases of unscarred uterus had blood transfusions. Higher number of transfusion rate was observed in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. Fetal malpresentation was observed in 30.8% of the patients.

Table 3: Fetal malpresentation among scarred and unscarred uterus

Fetal malpresentation	Scarred uterus	Unscarred uterus	P value
Vertex	49	31	0.986
Breech	25	15	
Transverse	6	4	

Among scarred uterus, 61.25% had vertex presentation, 31.25% had breech presentation and 7.5% had transverse presentation.

Among unscarred uterus, 62% had vertex presentation, 30% had breech presentation and 8% had transverse presentation.

Neonatal Outcomes

Low birth weight was seen in 56.25% cases of scarred uterus and 44% cases of unscarred uterus, though not statistically significant. Mean birth weight in the scarred uterus group was 2.34kgs and in the unscarred uterus group, it was 2.5kgs.

Table 4: Preterm birth

Preterm birth	Scarred uterus	Unscarred uterus	P value
Yes	42	21	0.162
No	38	29	

52.5% cases of scarred uterus and 42% cases of unscarred uterus had prematurity. There was no statistical association between previous LSCS and pre-term birth. 52.5% cases of scarred uterus and 36% cases of unscarred uterus needed NICU admission among the neonates.

Table 5: association of previous LSCS with NICU admission

		NICU Admission		Total	P value
		Yes	No		
Previous No of LSCS	NA	23	36	59	0.054
	1	26	27	53	
	2	11	7	18	
Total		60	70	130	

There was no statistical association between previous LSCS and NICU admission. One Still birth was observed in each scarred and unscarred uterus group.

Table 6: Association of still birth with previous LSCS

		Still Birth		Total	P Value
		Yes	No		
Previous No of LSCS	NA	1	58	59	0.423
	1	0	53	53	
	2	1	17	18	
Total		2	128	130	

80% of neonatal death was observed in scarred uterus group and 20% in unscarred uterus group.

Discussion

In a study by Ozkose ZG et al, six patients (7.5%) diagnosed with placenta previa undergoing emergency caesarean delivery required intensive care unit (ICU) admission. [1] In the present study, 90% patients admitted in ICU were cases of scarred uterus and 10% were cases of unscarred uterus. In this study we observed more blood transfusions (indicating high blood loss) and higher hysterectomy rates in scarred compared to unscarred uterus group. This could be the contributing factor for ICU admission.

Maternal Mortality: In a study by Mathuriya et al [2], there was only one maternal mortality in unscarred uterus and none in scarred uterus. Ahmed S et al's study demonstrates 7% mortality rate among patients with placenta previa. [3] A study by Crane JM et al showed no maternal deaths among placenta previa patients. [4]

In a study by Shrigiriwar M et al, maternal mortality occurred in three cases with scarred uterus and one case with unscarred uterus. [5] This study also demonstrated similar results with one mortality only in unscarred group. This could be a coincidental finding.

Blood transfusion

Blood transfusions occur more frequently in women with placenta previa. A study by Ahmed S et al

showed that the average units of donated blood were 2.5 ± 1.8 units with a maximum of 8 units in some cases. [3] In a study by Nair DB et al, >4 blood transfusions were significant association with scarred uterus. [6] Studies by Khansa showed 10% of patients with scarred uterus needed massive blood transfusion compared to no patients in the unscarred group. [7] In this study, higher number of transfusion rate was observed in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. As the need for blood transfusion is higher in scarred uterus, it becomes important that all obstetrical units caring for such patients be prepared for potential complications by providing adequate staffing, blood availability, and counseling of patients. [4]

Mean low birth weight

A study by Upreti R et al showed low birth weight was present in 28 cases in the scarred category compared to 15 cases in unscarred with p value 0.03 which was statistically significant. [8] In the present study, low birth weight was seen in 56.25% cases with scarred uterus and 44% cases with unscarred uterus, though not statistically significant

Preterm birth

Ahmed S et al's study showed incidence of prematurity (gestational age <37 weeks) among placenta previa cases was 13.5%. [3] A study by Katke RD et al observed that premature birth was observed in 66.7% women in the scarred uterus group as compared to 20% in unscarred group. [9] In a study by Mathuriya et al, where babies which were delivered at <37 weeks of gestation, 58% were cases of scarred uterus and 47% were cases of unscarred uterus. (2) A study by Shrigiriwar M et al [10], prematurity was observed in 63% of the cases with scarred uterus and 41% of the cases with unscarred uterus. $P = 0.032$ was considered to be statistically significant. A study by Upreti R et al showed preterm birth in 31 cases in the scarred category compared to 24 in the unscarred category. [8] In this study, 52.5% cases with scarred uterus and 42% cases with unscarred uterus resulted in prematurity. We could conclude that prematurity was more common in cases with scarred uterus as compared to unscarred uterus. Hence, patients diagnosed with placenta previa requires vigilant preparedness for risk factors. Placenta previa with scarred uterus could be an independent risk factor for pre-term birth.

Fetal malpresentation

Malpresentations are common in placenta previa; however, cephalic is still the most common presentation. However, in all these patients, the head was high floating or deflexed even at term. A study by Shrigiriwar M et al showed cephalic presentation was found in 84% cases with scarred uterus and 76% in unscarred uterus. Upreti R et al's study

showed malpresentation in 7 cases in scarred group compared to 1 case in unscarred with p value of 0.018 which was statistically significant. [8] A study by Parikh PM et al showed 24.2% cases with unscarred uterus and 26.6% with scarred uterus had fetal malpresentation. [11] In the present study, 30.8% of the patients had fetal malpresentation. Though studies show that cephalic presentation is common in placenta previa cases, there is high risk of malpresentation.

NICU admission

A study by Ahmed et al showed that among the infants delivered to patients with placenta previa, 20% required NICU admission. (3) Studies have shown that neonatal outcomes are much different among the scarred and unscarred groups. [4,8,12]. This study shows high NICU admission rates among scarred group compared to unscarred group.

Still birth

A study by Katke RD et al observed no still births in either groups. [9] Ahmed et al's study showed 13.2% still births among the placenta previa groups. [3] A study by Parikh PM et al showed 12.1% neonates in the unscarred group and 17.7% neonates in the scarred group had still births. [11] Our study demonstrated equal still birth among scarred and unscarred group.

Neonatal death

A study by Parikh PM et al showed a significantly higher incidence of neonatal death, 17.7% in the scarred uterus group as compared to 6.06% patients in the unscarred group. [11] A study by Katke et al demonstrated one neonatal death, which was in the scarred group. [9] In our study, 80% of neonatal deaths was observed in the scarred uterus group and 20% in unscarred uterus group.

A study by Shrigiriwar M et al, live birth occurred in 90% of the cases of scarred uterus and in 91% in case of unscarred uterus. Thus, it was found in this study that fetal outcome such as live birth, still-birth, and neonatal death did not differ much with the presence of scarred uterus. [10] In the study by Khatke et al, both scarred and unscarred groups showed a favourable fetal outcome (Group A 100%, Group B 96%). [9]

In this study, neonatal outcomes in terms of preterm birth, still birth, NICU admission and neonatal death did not differ statistically among the scarred and unscarred groups.

Studies have demonstrated that placenta previa was an independent risk factor for adverse neonatal outcomes irrespective of the scarring status of the uterus. [3] However, it becomes justifiable that the presence of placenta previa itself increases adverse neonatal outcomes when delivered at term. The reasons behind the effect of placenta previa on

fetal growth remains a matter of much debate among scientists, some argue that placenta previa is not an independent risk factor for impaired fetal growth and no significant difference in birth weight in neonates born to mothers with placenta previa and those delivered to normal placenta locations. [4]

Management of morbidly adherent placenta previa is challenging and requires a team approach as there are very high chances of caesarean hysterectomy in cases of morbidly adherent placenta previa with history of previous 1 or more LSCS.

It can be concluded that there is significant association of placenta praevia with previous surgery on uterus. Primary prevention in the form of reduction in the rate of primi caesarean section must be done in order to prevent likelihood of placenta previa in scarred uteri. Morbidity and mortality associated with placenta praevia and pathological placental adherence can be curtailed by routine screening of the scarred obstetric population for placental localization at an appropriate gestational period.

The emphasis should be on institutional delivery in a tertiary care centre with multidisciplinary care i.e. involvement of senior obstetrician, neonatologist, sonologist and haematologist. Early diagnosis by Ultrasound and planned delivery should be the goal.

Conclusion

Complete placenta previa, anterior placental position and adherent placenta were significantly associated with scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. Complete placenta previa, anterior location of placenta and adherent placenta had significant association with previous LSCS. Antepartum hemorrhage and postpartum hemorrhage was higher in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus.

Rate of caesarean hysterectomy was higher in scarred uterus, along with statistical association to previous LSCS.

Maternal ICU admission rate was higher in scarred group, also showed its statistical association with previous LSCS. Higher number of transfusion rate was observed in scarred uterus compared to unscarred uterus. Higher malpresentation was observed in unscarred uterus than in scarred uterus. Neonatal outcomes in terms of pre-term birth, still birth, NICU admission and neonatal death though higher in scarred group, did not differ statistically among the groups.

References

1. Gedik Özköse Z, Oğlak SC, Ölmez F. The comparison of maternal and neonatal outcomes between planned and emergency cesarean deliveries in placenta previa patients without placenta accreta spectrum. *Ginekol Pol.* 2022 Jan 24.
2. Mathuriya, G., & Lokhande, P. (2013). Comparative Study of Obstetrics Outcome between Scarred and Unscarred Uterus in Placenta Previa Cases. *Indian Journal Clin Pract*, 24.
3. Dashe JS, McIntire DD, Ramus RM, Santos-Ramos R, Twickler DM. Persistence of placenta previa according to gestational age at ultrasound detection. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2002 May; 99(5 Pt 1):692-7.
4. Crane JM, Van den Hof MC, Dodds L, Armonson BA, Liston R. Maternal complications with placenta previa. *Am J Perinatol.* 2000; 17(2):101-5.
5. Cunningham FG, Leveno KJ, Bloom SL et al. Obstetric haemorrhage. In: *Williams Textbook of Obstetrics*, 22nd ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 20 ;809-823
6. Nair DB, Murukesan L, Menon S. The effect of previous obstetric interventions in the outcome of placenta previa. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2017; 6(11):4879-85.
7. Iqbal K, Abid R, Irfan R, Shaheen F. Comparison of Fetomaternal Outcome Between Scarred and Unscarred Uterus in Placenta Previa Cases. *J Soc Obstet Gynecol Pak.* 2016; 6(3):102.
8. Upreti R, Rauniyar A, Rauniyar S, Ansari SN, Khadka M. A comparative study of obstetrics outcome of placenta previa in scarred versus unscarred uterus at tertiary Hospital, Kathmandu, Nepal. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2020 Aug; 9(8):3183-3187.
9. Katke RD. Placenta previa: outcomes in scarred and unscarred uterus. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2016 Aug; 5(8): 2728-2732.
10. Shrigiriwar M, Kesarwani S, Ramteke S. Fetomaternal Outcome in Placenta Previa in Scarred versus Non-scarred Uterus. *International Journal of Scientific Study.* Feb
11. Parikh, P. M., Makwana, S., Shah, S., & Vithalani, V. (2016). Feto-Maternal Outcome in Placenta Previa in Scarred Uterus Vs Non Scarred Uterus. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSR-JDMS)*, 15(1):69-73.
12. Ananth CV, Demissie K, Smulian JC, Vintzileos AM. Relationship among placenta previa, fetal growth restriction, and preterm delivery: a population-based study. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2001; 98:299-306.